

New Era in Research Development with the Launch of the EMERGE Resource Library for MSIs and ERIs

By Kimberly Eck and Japera Hemming

The National Organization of Research Development Professionals (NORDP) Consultants Program is committed to increasing the diversity of the US national research ecosystem by partnering with Minority-Serving and Emerging Research Institutions (MSIs and ERIs) to implement research development strategies at no cost to the institution. To date, the program has partnered with 172 institutions of higher education (IHEs), all of which are ERIs and 73 are MSIs (including 33 Historically Black Colleges or Universities (HBCUs), 26 Hispanic Serving Institutions (HSIs), and 14 other IHEs with designations, such as Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AANAPISIs), Alaska Native and Native Hawaiian Serving Institutions (ANNHs), Predominantly Black Institution (PBIs), and Native American-Serving Nontribal Institutions (NASNTIs) spanning 44 states and territories. More than 40 individuals support the NORDP Consultants Program, including 26 consultants, four expert research administrators, several peer mentors, advisory group members, and program leadership. Since the program's inception in 2021, MSIs and ERIs in the program have secured an incredible \$90.6M, including \$63.4M dedicated to building continued research capacity building activities and resources for their institutions.

Background

Research development is a function that seeks to grow research or increase the research reputation of an institution (Eck & Roney, 2022). Research development professionals most commonly engage in activities, such as identifying and disseminating funding opportunities, facilitating interdisciplinary collaborations, providing proposal development services, and reporting on success metrics (Eck & Roney, 2022). From an analysis of research development job descriptions and salary surveys, most research development professionals are employed by IHEs that are classified as R1: Doctoral Universities – Very high research activity according to the contemporaneous Carnegie Classifications or as a high-performing academic medical center not eligible to receive R1 status (Preuss et al., 2019; Preuss, et al., 2020) leaving MSIs and ERIs at a disadvantage when competing for research funding. Between 2010 and 2022, the top 150 research institutions based on total research expenditures, as reported in the Higher Education Research & Development (HERD) survey, grew by 70%, while more than other 500 IHEs saw only a 5% over the same time period (Pai et al., 2024). To address this disparity and further NORDP's deep dedication to diversity, equity, and inclusion, the NORDP Consultants Program was launched in 2021.

Program Structure

The NORDP Consultants Program utilizes three models of engagement: 1) intensive cohorts; 2) embedded proposal development; and 3) partner-initiated proposals. In the **intensive cohort** engagements, partnering institutions are paired with a team of NORDP Consultants to complete a three-phase process to build and implement strategic and sustainable plans that grow institutional capacity for research. A lead contact, who is often a leader within the institution's research infrastructure serves as the primary contact and implements the strategic plans with the consultants over two years. (Eck, 2023).

In the **embedded proposal development** model of engagement, a funding agency soliciting applications from MSIs and ERIs embeds NORDP Consultants in the application process to provide coaching and proposal development services to support the submission of competitive proposals. (Eck et al., 2023.) The NORDP Consultants Program also welcomes opportunities from MSIs and ERIs to collaborate with the NORDP Consultants Program to submit an external application that would support NORDP Consultants' engagement. If awarded, the institution is then paired with NORDP Consultants to conduct strategic planning and implement the desired research development activities. **Partner-initiated** requests to collaborate are evaluated individually. If the request aligns with the mission of the NORDP Consultants program and reasonable resources are available, the NORDP Consultants develops a custom scope of work to support the MSI or ERI in achieving their goals for the proposal and project.

EMERGE Resource Library

A key component of the NORDP Consultants Program is the creation of accessible and tailored resources. To this end, the NORDP Consultants Program enthusiastically announces the launch of the Equipping Minoritized and Emerging Research Institutions to Grow their Enterprises (EMERGE) Resource Library. The EMERGE Library is the first national library of collaboratively written and peer-reviewed plain language research enterprise guides that center the voice, perspective, and expertise of MSIs and ERIs. Importantly, all EMERGE topics were identified by and with MSIs and ERIs partnering with the NORDP Consultants Program.

The EMERGE Resource Library documents the research enterprise best practices and strategic innovation that MSIs and ERIs leverage to make substantive contributions to the US research enterprise. These resources cover a range of topics related to both research administration and research development, and are tailored for different audiences, including

faculty, research support staff, and research leadership. They offer practical guidance on implementing specific research enterprise skills, functions, services, or strategies.

Over time, the **EMERGE Resource Library**, designed by, with, and for research leaders across MSIs and ERI will continue to expand to include proposal development supports, research enterprise policy and process examples, guidelines for institutional goals, and other topics. The inaugural resources are accessible on the NORDP Consultants Program's website, including:

1. Brown, B. Hemming, J. and Eck, K. (2024) Mechanism Summary and Guide for Investigators: NIH R16 SURE and SURE-First. *National Organization of Research Development Professionals Consultants Program EMERGE Resource Library*.
2. Hawk, J., Koduvayur, S., and Scholz, C. (2024). Mechanism Summary and Guide for Investigators: NIH R15. *National Organization of Research Development Professionals Consultants Program EMERGE Resource Library*.
3. Correa, L., Jager, B., and Steenrod, S. (2024). Mechanism Summary and Guide for Investigators: NSF CAREER. *National Organization of Research Development Professionals Consultants Program EMERGE Resource Library*.

Conclusion

Through its engagements thus far, the NORDP Consultants Program has proven the effectiveness of its consultant-driven model in providing tailored research development support to MSIs and ERIs. The program's multi-faceted approach, which includes strategic planning, proposal development, and targeted capacity-building, has demonstrated measurable

Table 1: Three-Phase Engagement Framework

Phase	Key Activities
Phase 1: Intake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultants collect and review institutional strategic plans, proposal and award data, information on centers and institutes, recent assessments or faculty feedback, and similar documents • Consultants interview key stakeholders, such as vice president for research and staff, deans, associate deans for research, and successful researchers to hone goals for the research enterprise, barriers, successes, and existing resources
Phase 2: Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultants summarize information received • Consultants identify potential areas for improvement in collaboration with MSIs • Consultants, through an Engagement Plan Template, document institutional goals for advancing the research enterprise as well as activities to achieve these goals (this is an iterative drafting process conducted in collaboration with MSI partner)
Phase 3: Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultants implement Engagement Plan activities • Consultants revisit remainder of Engagement Plan and make revisions, as needed

impacts on the research capabilities of participating institutions. The substantial amount of funding secured by these institutions—over \$90 million since the program’s inception—is a testament to the transformative potential of dedicated research development support.

The NORDP Consultants Program is not just an initiative; it represents a critical step toward expanding the national research ecosystem and thoughtfully supporting MSIs/ERIs making innovative contributions to science and other disciplines. By fostering meaningful partnerships and providing bespoke research development strategies, the program enables these institutions to play a more prominent role in the national research ecosystem.

However, the work does not stop here. As the NORDP Consultants Program continues to expand, it invites new MSIs and ERIs to participate in this transformative initiative. Institutions interested in scaling their research capabilities, securing competitive funding, and implementing sustainable research development strategies are encouraged to take the next step and apply to be a part of the cohort model and begin a discussion about a partner-initiated proposal.

Call to Action

If your institution is looking to strengthen its research infrastructure, collaborate on impactful research projects, or access resources that will drive long-term success, the NORDP Consultants Program wants to hear from you. Visit the [NORDP Consultants Program](#) website to explore partnership opportunities, review program models, and access the groundbreaking EMERGE Resource Library. Here, you will find the tools and resources necessary to accelerate your institution’s research ambitions. ■

References

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Information Telescope: How to See Research News on the Horizon

By *Csilla M. Csaplár*

In our world of information overload, it can be taxing to keep up with the barrage of policy, regulation, and process changes. It is harder still to know how these changes impact your team and your institution. To keep up with news as it appears on the horizon, consider using these resources:

Sponsor and association listservs

This is the easiest place to start as listservs provide opportunities to be part of the dialogue around our collective challenges. Be sure to curate what you receive and focus on what is most relevant to your role. Establish email filters so you don’t flood your inbox, and set aside time periodically to skim for important highlights.

Governmental relations partners

If your campus has a governmental relations team, arrange to meet them. They often share pertinent information with campus partners. Even if you’re not the decision-maker, it is helpful to know (and be able to ask questions) about issues your campus and your colleagues are encountering.

Communities practice

Participating in a community of practice engages a network of peers to crowd-source solutions, vet your interpretation or implementation plan, and learn best practices. Seek (or create!) one within peer roles at your institution, local region, state college system, or sports conference.

Teach approach

With so many sponsors, funding mechanisms, systems, and more, we feel like we must know everything, which is not a reality for even the most experienced research administrators! I encourage teams to learn how to approach a new solicitation, agreement, policy, task, etc., rather than memorize specific details of each sponsor. Instead of creating a static checklist, consider areas of responsibility for a task or project. This will help you identify what to look for, including what may be missing, and tailor your review to the circumstance. This takes practice and exposure, but is a great way to develop confidence and problem-solving skills so you are ready for the next new thing. ■

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